

Purpose: Relative changes in event rates are a common primary endpoint in confirmatory asthma trials, and reliable assumptions about baseline event rates and extra-Poisson variability are essential for valid sample size planning. Using an example application in asthma, we aim to synthesize placebo-group exacerbation data, evaluate calendar-time trends, and assess implications for trial design.

Methods: We conducted a systematic review of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) reporting recurrent asthma exacerbations. Placebo-group outcomes were synthesized using a hierarchical negative binomial model accommodating heterogeneous reporting formats and jointly modeling event rates and overdispersion. Meta-regression was used to adjust for calendar-time trends in order to predict event rates for the design of a future trial.

Results: Sixty-two trials met inclusion criteria. The overall analysis corresponded to an estimated relative change of 1.8% per year (95% CI: -7.4%, 4.3%), equivalent to 16.3% per decade. Substantial between-study heterogeneity in both event rates and overdispersion was observed. The posterior mean overdispersion parameter was 0.382. In a representative phase III scenario, incorporating this level of dispersion increased required sample sizes by approximately 23% compared with Poisson-based assumptions.

Conclusion: Event rates in clinical trials exhibit considerable heterogeneity and potential temporal variation, and overdispersion represents a critical design parameter. Comprehensive modelling of recurrent-event endpoints allows for evidence-based and robust sample size calculations and trial design.